

GODAN: A Study in Existential Humanism

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Godan, Prem Chand's last completed novel, is considered to be his best work. The novel depicts the tragedy and pathos of the dark lives and unceasing sorrows of the peasantry of India. Prem Chand's most outstanding novel, where he has portrayed the characters with deep understanding of their emotions. He has created them with utmost tenderness and honesty. The central character, Hori is unparalleled and unsurpassed in the whole Indian fiction. Hori, the representative of the helpless peasantry of India, speaks out about his existential problems, on the very first page;

It's all due to keeping good terms with the master that trouble has remained at arm's length from us otherwise we would have been wiped out of existence long ago.

(Godan, p-1)

Premchand has depicted the pathos, unceasing sorrows and frustrations of a common man with sympathetic understanding. According to Dr. Kamal Kishore Goyanka, 'Godan presents the terrible problems of

existence of peasant life.' The novel exposes the social, economic and religious absurdities. As Dr. Shailaish Zaidi has suggested in his book, Godan: Ek Navya Drishti, Premchand was quite aware of the world of philosophy of human freedom besides his awareness of social and political India. To Premchand, human freedom was the central fact. He has very deftly shown a poor peasant struggling for his freedom.

Hori is a tragic hero as his socio-economic pressures don't allow him to assert his freedom of choice. Apart from poverty, he is bound by the social values. He bears a lot many pains to keep his name in the society. He and his wife belong to a society where most of the people submit their personal choice to the social order to keep up a good name. Indian peasants, as it's clearly revealed in the novel, don't worry about their daily comforts of food and clothing but with all their strength they maintain a good name in their society. They live and die for a good name. It is due to this reason that when Dhania comes to know about Jhunia's elopement with Gobar she says, 'has smeared our name'. they could have thrown away Jhunia to save their reputation

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which would have been more acceptable to the orthodox society. But they assert their individual freedom against the social conventions by sheltering Jhunia in their house. They accepted the enmity of Jhunia's father and the penalty from the community to keep up their humanism. This episode justifies their humanity and individuality as against the system which crushes individual choice. At a later stage, Dhania, Hori, his wife helps Selia, low caste women by giving her a shelter, this was another revolutionary step against the general will of the community. It needed great courage to go against the existing order to assert individual choice for a semi-starved, struggling person. Dhania is a rebel who fights for humanity. She even stands against the police inspector in presence of the headman of the village, she has the courage to rebel against those who regulate the flow of social tradition. She answers boldly to the inspector;

"So what?" Dhania said snapping her fingers. "It was my cow that I poisoned. If your investigation leads you to this conclusion, arrest me. I've seen enough of your justice and intelligence...I've nothing to do with such a loan. And if you want to give someone, let this man accounts for the loan. I won't pay a paisa even if I am dragged to the magistrate's court.

(Godan, p-85)

As Albert Camus suggests, rebellion is courageous; it's a rising of consciousness. We realize that in the

revolutionary acts and decisions, it is Dhania's rising conscious that compels her for revolution. Her revolt is a conscious affirmation of her humanity against the social conventions.

Hori continues to struggle throughout his hopeless life. He does not revolt openly but at the same time he never thinks of renouncing the world. At times he is defeated by the destiny but he never tries to run away from his responsibilities. The reader finds Hori's life to be hopeless and optimistic throughout his life. Hori represents the Indian peasantry of the period, who were hungry and semi-starved, yet hopeful and optimistic. In a life which is restricted by economic, social and religious barriers, Hori still has a choice. The choice for Hori remains between life and death. He doesn't choose death and peace thereby; but life and struggle. As Albert Camus suggests, suicide is a logical answer to the irrational universe but it is the consummation of the defeated conscience. Hori's conscience is not defeated. He doesn't find a single reason to give up his struggle for existence. Those who call Hori 'a representative' of the defeated peasantry, might have to re-read Godan. Hori isn't defeated His victory lies in his efforts; his responsibilities that he shoulders honestly. Whether he got fruitful results of his efforts, isn't a qualifying question. "Karmanye Vadhikaraste Ma Phaleshu Kadachain" (Bhagwat Gita).

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Gobar, Hori's son, believes in making his own destiny. He doesn't believe in a preordained life. In an answer to Hori's statement, "It's God who creates the high and low", Gobar says; "these are fancies, only to console the mind. God creates us equal. Those who have power oppress the poor and become rich." (Godan, p-18).

Gobar believes that God is responsible only for our existence and not the essence. Once a man comes into the world, he gets what he can do to get by his own power and choice. He is a rebel like his mother, he dreams a better life and believes in changeability. His dreams get an opportunity to take a practical shape in his life. When he come to the city, he doesn't become rich but certainly better off. He gets an opportunity to come out of the rural orthodoxy. But soon he falls a victim to bad habits and makes his life pitiable. This was an effect of the mill worker-culture. Premchand is critical of such culture which urbanization and industrialization have brought with them.

The type of life a mill worker gets is, tiring and monotonous. Although

Gobar worked in the village but his work in city in the sugar mill was absolutely tiring:

In village he had to put in the equally hard work, But he had never felt tired. In the open fields, under the sky, even if he felt tired after the day's work his mind remained light. Here even if he

did a little work, the sped and deafening roar of the machines made him high strung. In addition was the constant fear of being pulled up for laxity or mistake in performance of duty. This state of mind was not peculiar to Gobar alone; it affected all workers.

(Godan, p-225)

As we know existentialism is critical of industrialization and urbanization, the above piece of description is truly existential. To work in one's own fields represents a work with more personal freedom than a work being done in a mill for another person. Hori, a more experienced peasant, knew this difference and that is why even a dream of becoming a labour or taking up a job under another person, terrified him. Although he knows that, "A servant with a salary of ten rupees a month is better off than us (his family). But we do not give up our land and go for a job." (Godan, p-17)

To become a servant is to submit one's individual freedom totally to the master. Hori didn't want that. He was very much familiar with the unceasing sorrows of a peasant life, yet he remains a farmer by his choice throughout his life. To own a piece of land was symbolic of being the owner of the one's own will. The feeling of loss of freedom had been a personal experience of Permchand. He did get an attractive remuneration for the scripts he wrote but had no freedom of choice. He had to write as per the demand of the producer and it was tiring. Soon it

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become suffocating for him and he came back to embrace poverty which had freedom of thought with it.

The high mechanical life of the city doesn't only affect Gobar but also his wife, Jounia and their children Lallu. Jhunia suffers from a marital crisis where as Gobar suffers from a sexual crisis. His regular demands on his wife and the mechanical life with no one to talk to, make Jhunia a distraught person.

Within short times she was fed up with this sort of life. She wanted solitude; she wanted to sleep and laze, where could one get such solitude in the city?

(Godan, p-225)

It is to be noted that she did not have anyone to talk to yet had no solitude. This is a typical existential problem of the modern, crowded cities. Man feels lonely in a crowd. There is so much of noise to baffle the mind yet there is nothing to listen to. Not only the adults but the children of the modern generation are trapped in small houses in cities which have no open playground left. Gobar's child who was just come from village where he had enough open space to play, feels irritated in a closed house.

Their (Gobar and Jhunia's) child, used to play in open, had to remain cooped up in the house; the passage on which the door opened was hardly a yard wide and exhaled a shocking stench. there was hardly any space worth

the name to stretch oneself. Having no one to play with, the child clung to his mother. In the village he had Rupa and Sona and others.

(Godan, p-224)

Be it a child, a housewife, a mill worker or a mill owner, a zamindar or a field worker, everyone's freedom is restricted by various forces. Premchand depicts all of them sailing in their own life boats and struggling against the harsh waves of worldly pressures.

Though it is said that Premchand is an Idealist and a socialist, in his masterpieces we find various passages to confirm that towards the end of his literary career he had surely realized that happiness comes through individual freedom and not merely by economic equality. He has shown in this novel that the rich and the poor are both oppressed by the worldly pressures. If poverty restricts the individual freedom of the poor, social prestige and self pride gets in the way of the rich. It is true that Premchand is more sympathetic towards the poor and socially underprivileged, but he has a sharp insight into the agonies of the rich as well. Godan portrays a large variety of characters from various levels of society, each tied in his or her own socio-economic and emotional strings. Each character of the novel (which has around 103 named and unnamed characters) is fixed in definite socio-economic niche. Most of the characters have complaints from the world around,

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but they still continue to interact with absurd world. As the existentialists believe, 'the meaninglessness of the life is not in death but in the fact that one lives in the irrational, absurd and unjust world.' Man understands the absurdities of the world but cannot dissolve it. The Rai Saheb, who is thought to be happy person owning to his wealth, says:

The world thinks we are happy; we own lands, palaces, carriages, scores of servants to wait on us and concubines for our diversion. But I believe firmly that person without self respect and spiritual strength is not fit to be called a man. A person who cannot sleep peacefully for fear of the enemy, who licks the shoes of the officials and sucks the blood of his people cannot be called happy. When the British officer comes out on a tour or on a hunt I follow him like a shadow; afraid of him and I freeze to death. To what length I go to make him happy...! Indolence has crippled us; we have no confidence life is our perseverance...the flattery of toadies has made us so arrogant, that the sense of tolerance, modesty and services, has died out in our hearts.

(Godan, pp. 14-15)

Rai Sahab calls himself a victim of circumstances'. We notice that Rai Sahab is in debts as Hori is; he begs for his daughter's marriage as Hori does for

his. Rai Sahab's situation is as pathetic as that of Hori. A slight difference between their conditions is that if Rai Sahab will strongly, he may break off his social bondages but Hori, in spite of his strongest desires, cannot afford to go against social conventions.

Rai Saheb is thought to be a hypocrite by many of us as also by Gobar when Rai Saheb explains to Hori:

Sometimes I think the government will be actually doing us a favour if it deprives us of our lands... I am ready for that day. It will be a day of redemption. We are ready of circumstances and as long as we are shackled with property we shall not be able to lead a life of dignity.

(Godan, p-15)

On listening this from Hori, Gobar calls Rai Saheb a hypocrite. Gobar cannot realize a man owning palaces and a dozen cars to be unhappy. Having born and brought up in an underprivileged economic situation, Gobar thinks material wealth to be the key happiness. But we know that there are more unhappy and unsatisfied people among the poor. Kings often spend sleepless nights while a gipsy sleeps well. 'Happiness is a habit' and there is no direct relationship between happiness and material wealth. Gobar does not understand this and angrily says:

if Rai Saheb is unhappy, 'why doesn't the Rai Saheb change places with us?... 'We shall

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gradually give him our land, plough and bullocks. All we have in fact. Will he agree to this deal?

(Godan, p-17)

Gobar does not realize that exchanging social places is not easy specially in an orthodox and rigid society of his. His father Hori explains to him thus;

Does anybody ever give up his ancestral property? Look at us for instance. What do we get out of our land? The return does not even equal an anna's wage Per head...But we do not give up our land and go in for a job. Do we? Our prestige gets in the way. Well, that's exactly the case with the zanindar.

(Godan, p-17)

Those who think that Rai Sahab is trying to gain sympathy by saying all that mentioned, are not mistaken, Rai Saheb is indeed trying to gain sympathies for himself. But at the same time what he says has a touch of reality. It may be comparable to the act of a beggar who exposes his wounds to gain sympathies of the passing public. The act is purposely done for a selfish cause. Yet we can't deny the reality of the beggar's wounds. Similarly Rai Saheb is taking of his real problems but for a selfish cause.

At another instance when Rai Saheb is angry and out of his control, he speaks out the truth which lies behind his exterior pomp and show. This time it was

not Hori, to whom he was talking but it was Pandit Omkarnath.

Pandit Omkarnath an editor of a newspaper, was not a simpleton like Hori who couldn't understand the words of Rai Saheb and its hidden meaning. Rai Saheb was certainly not trying to impress Omkarnath by his words. It was the truth of the condition which came out of his mouth in rage;

...Not that we are poisonous scorpions out to sting everyone; nor does it pleas us too oppress the poor. But we must uphold the dignity and tradition of our line. You take advantage of my position, don't you: There are scores of others for whom I am the goose eggs. Come to my bungalow my friend, and I will show you how they make me the target of their attack every damned minute of the day. One dealer tries to palm off a Kashmir shawl on me, another dumps me with tobacco and perfumes; another canvasses for books and periodicals; one sells life insurances, another a gramophone; and endless swarms of donation hunters! All have an eye on my pocket. If I stop keeping up why appearances, why I'll expose myself the officials I'll be dubbed a reactionary. Will you save me from ridicule then? I joined the Congress and I am still paying the

price I have been black listed by the government. Have you ever cared to know the extent of my debts? If all the moneylenders get decree against me, I shan't be left with this ring on my figure.

(Godan, p-43)

This view must be astonishing to many, as it was to the editor, Omkarnath, but it is nearer the reality. In the modern times, poverty is not forced on a few peculiar sects of the society. At least in our country, if someone is poor, it is more due to his own indifference towards materialistic prosperity. With the changed social situation which gives equal opportunities of success to everyone, irrespective of caste, creed and religion, there is a little economic injustice. Anyone sensible, courageous, hard-working and patient can earn a direct living. With the end of the feudal system and advent of scientific technology, earning a living has become easier. The modern world's not related much to poverty but to the mechanical pace of life, loss of identity, rootlessness, solitude and emotional crisis. The existential writers concentrate themselves on these problems. However, when Dr. Mehta speaks against the Marxist philosophy, he is a bit ahead of his age. This is why he astonishes many by his views. He further explains his views as follows:

By hook or by crook you might succeed in distriputing wealth. But how can you make an equitable distribution of intelligence and character and beauty and health? It's not wealth alone that sets up the high and grades down the low.

(Godan, p-44)

(Godan, p-137)

It can be seen in the above description that even Rai Saheb has his own social restrictions. Every individual has his own social limitations to restrict freedom of choice. When the social bondages become too tight for a man, he rebels against it. There are evidences in the novel which affirm Premchand's disillusionment from socialism and a move toward existentialism. According to a famous critic of Premchand, Ram Vilas Sharama:

If Mehta and Hori could be combined, the personage formed thus, would be similar to Premchand. If he (Premchand) has given his views to Mehta, he has given the will power for continuous labour to Hori.

(Godan, p-106)

If Dr. Mehta has the views of Munshi Premchand himself, Dr. Mehta's words must be representation of Premchand's mind and thoughts. Premchand's cherished character, Dr Mehta says:

I believed in the theory that the rich and the poor will always be with us. And that is it should be. Wiping out distinction will lead to social chaps.

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Dr. Mehta is a philosopher and has read the philosophies of the world. He believes in the freedom of the individual like the existentialist. Giving his views on the institution of marriage which delimits freedom and adds responsibilities, he says; "Marriage puts fences all around you." On being asked, which he considered superior, Marriage of remaining single, he replies; "From the point of view of the society marriage, from the point of the individual, being single."

(Godan, p-49)

Like a true existentialist he loves individual freedom. Dr. Mehta has been shown without a family. He lives alone. His freedom is not restricted by any factor associated with family. Yet his freedom doesn't lead him to a life without values. He creates his own values in order to comprehend the true meaning of his existence. He expresses his genuine humanity in all his behaviour.

It can be said that Godan is an extential novel as it is a realistic representation of the relationship between individual and his surrounding. It provides a true picture of the absurdities of the society and preaches to face the absurdities and not to run away. According to Dr. Shalesh Zaidi, an eminent critic of Premchand, "Hori of Godan belongs to the age of Albert Camus which (the age) knows that it is impossible to change the world." (Zaidi, p-37). Hori understands the absurdities

of the society but finds himself incapable of changing the world. The tragedy of Godan is that Hori lives with the absurdities of the world.

Dr. Shailish Zaidi writes about the author of Godan thus: Writers' awareness of his age gives us a picture of the historical situations of the nation at one hand and builds up a harmony with the international thought on the other hand. His thought keeps a reference to an awareness of nation and time. As a result neither he cuts himself from his environment nor he remains a mere professor of foreign thought. He rises above the feudal values of victory and defeat "Paap" and "Punya" and good and evil; and regards freedom as a central force of man. That is why they are related to the personal decision of man. Firmness of decision only provides man his freedom.

(Godan: Ek Navya Dristi, p-36-37)

In Hori's struggle and existence Hori doesn't accept his defeat and exercises his freedom of decision and partly due to his circumstances. He makes many wrong choices in his life for which he pays later. Premchand depicts him with all his follies and weaknesses. In spite of all his fragilities readers sympathy goes with him. Hori's character guides us to take up the challenges of life. He wanted to keep up his land and thereby his peasant life.

